

Research Article

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Print media representation of Islam in the context of terrorism in Kenya: Implications on counter-extremism strategies

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Abstract: In the 2025 Global Terrorism Index Report, the number of countries experiencing terrorist incidents increased from 58 to 66, with an evident upsurge in attacks. Kenya was ranked among the top 20 worst-hit countries in the world. Another report released by the Kenyan government in 2024 found that more than 500 lives had been lost to terrorism between 1998 and 2023. In these attacks, the media have linked terrorism to Islam, labeling Muslims as 'terrorists'; associating them with broader violent networks, and reinforcing stereotypes that fuel radicalisation, targeting over 2 billion Muslims worldwide. Newspaper representations of Islam and Muslims as terrorism sympathisers have fueled Islamophobia and promoted harmful stereotypes targeting the Muslim population across the globe. These biased narratives have led to mistrust and discrimination, significantly

undermining crucial counter-extremism strategies put in place by law enforcers and policymakers. Although this area has attracted many studies, the situation is still worsening globally, further risking alienation, radicalisation, and discrimination. The scenario, therefore, calls for more in-depth research to understand this phenomenon better and to provide solutions. This study, therefore, developed two objectives to unravel the research problem. It analysed how print media in Kenya represent Islam in the context of terrorism and then assessed the influence of such representations on counter-extremism strategies in Kenya. The study was guided by gatekeeping and social identity theories. It adopted a descriptive research design and mixed-methods approach for data collection, analysing 676 copies of The Standard and Nation newspapers for qualitative data, complemented by interviews with 24 key informants drawn from journalists, religious leaders, media scholars, and counter-terrorism/security experts. Quantitatively, the study measured the frequency of words and phrases linking Islam to terrorism. Findings have indicated that Kenya's print media have represented Islam as a terrorism sympathiser.

Keywords – Counter-extremism, Media, News coverage, Print media, Radicalisation, Terrorism

1. INTRODUCTION

Media content has long been considered a double-edged sword that is capable of either promoting peace or inciting people to violence. This duality has become central to debates surrounding terrorism and extremism. The discourses argue that while some audiences may interpret media narratives as glorifying violence, in other quarters, the same

stories are viewed by others as tools of liberation; a context where media is not merely a vehicle for information dissemination but is seen and embraced as a powerful agent in shaping ideology, identity, and freedom.

This blame game was evident in Kenya between 2024 and 2025 during the Generation Z (Gen Z) protests. According to the protesters and the human rights activists who joined them, as reported by Firstpost Africa TV (September 14, 2025), they were protesting against poor governance, which they argued was taking a toll on President William Ruto's government. However, the government, on the other hand, arrested some of the protesters and charged them with terrorism. The government stated that the protests were acts of terrorism and arraigned those arrested in court.

The portrayal of Islam as a terrorist in print media has exacerbated widespread Islamophobia and reinforced harmful stereotypes against over 2 million Muslims globally, undermining counter-extremism strategies (Khalil, 2021). This biased narrative fosters mistrust and discrimination, hindering law enforcement and policymakers from building trust and promoting peaceful coexistence between Muslims and non-Muslims.

In Kenya, print media coverage of terrorism has similarly framed Islam as perpetrator or sympathiser of terrorism, reinforcing damaging stereotypes. For example, as the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC, 2024) reported, the media reporting of the Westgate Mall shooting associated Islam with terrorism, which made Kenya's Muslims feel targeted, feeling that they became the focus of the security forces, leading to a deterioration in relations between Muslims and non-Muslims in Kenya.

This has led to government counter-extremism measures such as the Operation Usalama Watch and Operation Linda Nchi being accused of disproportionately targeting Kenyan-Somali Muslims, further fueling radicalisation (Amnesty International, 2014). Such print media coverage shapes public opinion, legitimises human rights violations, and perpetuates anti-Muslim prejudice, according to Khalil (2021). In a response to rising anti-Islam hate, terrorism, and violent extremism, the United Nations has advocated stronger measures, including peace frameworks like the Rabat Plan of Action and Faith for Rights, to foster dialogue, tolerance, and coexistence (UN, 2024).

This calls for more detailed interventions than military and security measures alone. The UN appeals for greater emphasis, such as working on security structures, enhancing community engagements, building stronger resilience, and balancing media narratives that promote human rights and collaboration. Despite existing research on this problem, there remains a pressing need for an updated study examining Kenyan print media's representation of Islam in the context of terrorism and its implications for counter-extremism efforts. This study, therefore, sought to provide contemporary recommendations for ethical media reporting to mitigate bias, enhance counter-extremism cooperation, and support peacebuilding. The findings are expected to contribute to a deeper understanding of terrorism dynamics by offering evidence-based strategies for responsible print media coverage, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal (SGD) Sixteen of Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions, Kenya's Vision 2030 of social and political pillars, and the African Union's Agenda 2063's fourth Aspiration of a Peaceful and Secure Africa.

Objectives:

1. To examine print media representation of Islam in the context of terrorism in Kenya.
2. To assess the influence of the representation on counter-extremism strategies in Kenya.y and paste from your manuscript.

Research Questions

1. How does print media represent Islam in the context of terrorism in Kenya?
2. How does the representation influence counter-extremism strategies in Kenya?

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

This study adopted Gatekeeping and Social Identity theories to answer the research questions and to help unravel the phenomenon.

2.1. The Theory of Gatekeeping

Gatekeeping refers to the human or technological processes employed to manage the flow of information. It is a critical concept in understanding how news is produced, filtered, and consumed. In journalism, gatekeeping is often described as the process whereby news content is sifted and refined, much like flour being sieved, to create narratives that align with the standards, values, and understanding of journalists, editors, and their audiences. The concept of gatekeeping originated in the 1940s with social psychologist Kurt Lewin. His initial study focused on the selection and distribution of food items within social systems in the United States, aiming to understand how resources are allocated (Erzikova, 2018). This study adopted this theory to answer the first research question and to understand the first objective. It delves into the process of news writing and editing. In this research, Gatekeeping theory has provided an effective understanding of how reporters went out to the field to cover the terrorist attacks, chose what they felt was more newsworthy, and, during writing and editing, let the contents reach the audience. Therefore, this research has addressed the first objective by examining the reporting and editing process-how stories about Islam were selected, framed, and potentially stereotyped as terrorism sympathisers.

This editorial gatekeeping stage has critical implications, as it may contribute to negative portrayals that influence public attitudes, as has been evident in the representation of Islam regarding terrorism in Kenya.

2.2. Social Identity Theory (SIT) Theory

Social Identity Theory (SIT) initially emerged as a framework for understanding intergroup relations and cooperation but has since evolved into a broader social psychological theory (McKeown et al., 2016). The theory defines a group as a collection of individuals who share a sense of belonging to the same social category. It posits that people derive their sense of self-worth and identity from their group memberships. According to Harwood (2025), the central premise of SIT is that individuals strive to achieve a positive social identity, which often leads them to favour their own groups while discriminating against others.

Developed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner in the 1970s, the theory highlights the human tendency to differentiate oneself from others based on group affiliation. Tajfel and Turner argued that individuals are often willing to "sacrifice absolute levels of rewards to maintain relative superiority over members of other groups" (Harwood, 2025: 1). Once individuals are categorised into a particular group, they naturally seek to enhance the group's status to gain positive feelings and reinforce their identity.

Against this backdrop, Social Identity Theory helps explain the link between negative media representation and social tension. When Muslims in Kenya feel demonised and devalued in the media, they may react defensively, sometimes through radicalisation or acts of terrorism as a form of retaliation. On the other hand, non-Muslims may also feel that Muslims are a threat to their lives and stand to fight back. This dynamic significantly undermines counter-terrorism efforts and complicates peacebuilding initiatives in the region. Therefore, the two theories have amicably answered the two objectives and the research questions for this study.

2.3. Print Media Representation of Islam in the Context of Terrorism

The aftermath of the September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks marked a paradigmatic shift in global security discourse and the print media portrayal of Islam, fundamentally altering public perceptions and state policies worldwide. This watershed moment catalysed the widespread adoption of the concept of "new terrorism," a term frequently propagated through print and broadcast media to underscore an alleged emergent threat characterized by religiously motivated extremism (Mythen, Walklate & Khan, 2000).

However, this framing was neither neutral nor benign. It substantially contributed to the social construction of Muslim minorities as inherently suspect populations, perpetually cast as potential terrorist threats requiring heightened surveillance and control by state apparatuses (Spalek, 2010). The hegemonic power of Western media in framing Islam and Muslims within the terror discourse is well documented across interdisciplinary studies

(Thiong'o, 2016). Influenced by Edward Said's foundational critique of Orientalism (1978), contemporary scholars argue that Western newsrooms often reproduce reductive, monolithic portrayals of Islam as an inherently violent and backward religion (Said, 2002).

Such framing not only simplifies complex geopolitical realities but also engenders a pernicious conflation between Islam and terrorism that misleads public understanding and fuels Islamophobia (Poole, 2002; Richardson, 2004). Khan's (2000) analysis of media narratives during the 1990 Gulf War highlights this phenomenon, revealing how Islam was erroneously conflated with Saddam Hussein's regime despite the conflict's primarily political and strategic dimensions. This misrepresentation continued post-9/11; Abdullah and Halim (2007) demonstrated how Australian media amplified stories linking Islam with violence disproportionately, thereby perpetuating a moral panic around Islamic communities. Similarly, Zinn (2007) critiques the evident double standard in Western media; that while state violence conducted by Western powers abroad is rarely framed negatively, Muslim-majority countries and their peoples are routinely vilified and criminalised in news narratives.

The persistence of such biased framing sustains an ideological discourse that legitimises securitisation policies, normalises racial profiling, and justifies restrictive immigration and surveillance regimes (Fekete, 2004). It is critical to recognise that these media representations are not simply reflections of reality but active agents in producing and reproducing societal fears and policy responses toward Muslim communities. Terrorist groups such as al-Qaeda have strategically leveraged media to amplify the psychological impact of their attacks. In a 2005 letter from al-Qaeda leader Ayman al-Zawahiri to Abu Musab al-Zarqawi, the critical role of media in terrorist operations was made explicit. Zawahiri stated, "More than half of the battle is taking place on the battlefield of the media. We are in a media race for hearts and minds" (Schmid, 2023: 560).

This view was echoed by Osama bin Laden in a letter to Emir al-Mominee, where he asserted, "It is obvious that the media war in this century is one of the strongest methods; in fact, its rating may reach 90 percent of the total preparation for the battles" (Schmid, 2023: 560). The media, in reporting acts of terror, often inadvertently become conduits for terrorists' messages. As one German terrorist, Hans-Joachim Klein, once remarked, "If they do not listen to us, then we throw a couple of bombs...we give the media what they need: newsworthy events. They cover us, explain our causes, and this unknowingly legitimates us" (as cited in Schmid, 2023: 568). Terrorist organisations have developed a keen understanding of what constitutes newsworthiness. According to Schmid (2023), terrorist acts are often staged to meet criteria that ensure media coverage: novelty, drama, surprise, human interest, and disruption.

These factors align with the long-standing media mantra, "If it bleeds, it leads," reflecting the commercial logic of news media that prioritize emotionally charged, violent, or sensational stories. Schmid observes that terrorists tailor their attacks to fit the "news system" to gain free publicity that would otherwise cost millions in paid media placements (p. 568). This media exploitation was especially evident in the September 11, 2001, attacks. Osama bin Laden had previously hinted at such plans, stating in a 1997 interview, 'ou'll see them and hear about them in the media, God willing' (as cited in Schmid, 2023: 569). Terrorists deliberately manufacture what Schmid describes as 'bad news' to dominate headlines, exploiting the media's own structural tendencies. The old newsroom adage-'bad news is good news, good news is bad news, and no news is bad news'- is thus co-opted by terrorist groups to amplify their message. In doing so, the media inadvertently become unwitting allies in the dissemination of terrorist propaganda.

Even though much attention is focused on the Western media's role in shaping public perceptions, it is equally important to interrogate how terrorist organizations engage with print and broadcast media to advance their strategic objectives. Rashid (2013) provides a comprehensive account of media manipulation under Taliban rule in Afghanistan, where the regime imposed a strict monopoly over information dissemination through the closure of independent outlets and the establishment of a state-controlled radio station. This monopolisation of media ensured the Taliban's narrative remained dominant, suppressing dissenting voices and limiting alternative perspectives. This phenomenon is emblematic of broader trends wherein terrorist groups seek to exploit the media's reach to amplify their ideological messages, attract recruits, and instill fear among target populations (Nacos, 2007). Conversely, by

controlling the flow of information, these groups aim to delegitimise opposing narratives, highlighting the complex symbiotic relationship between terrorism and media.

Media framing plays a critical role in shaping public perception of international conflicts. It influences whether a party is seen as a victim, aggressor, hero, or villain. As Galtung (2002) observed, media narratives often reflect the geopolitical interests of the countries where media outlets are based. Kenya exemplifies the global patterns of media bias in the local context. Kenyan print media have persistently portrayed Islam as a terrorist sympathiser, particularly following attacks like the Garissa University massacre, claimed by Al-Shabaab as motivated by religious antagonism (Odhiambo et al., 2015, as cited in Kamau, 2023). Such portrayals often mirror Western ideological frameworks, sometimes attributing failures of governance and security apparatuses to Islam rather than to structural issues (Schaeter, 2006).

Therefore, media framing is not a neutral process; it carries significant power in shaping how conflicts are understood and responded to globally. Moving toward constructive journalism and challenging geopolitical biases in media coverage can play a vital role in fostering more informed and empathetic public discourse. Misrepresentation exemplifies what scholars term the 'politicisation of Islamophobia,' where print media narratives reinforce dominant power structures and justify violent state actions under the guise of combating terrorism (El-Tayeb, 2011). The media sometimes allow stories to pass without fact-finding, therefore feeding the audience with rumour and propaganda, which can easily promote confusion, conflict, and interfere with terrorism mitigation strategies (Gambo, 2024).

Such biased coverage exacerbates global Islamophobic sentiments, deepens intergroup divisions, and impedes prospects for conflict resolution grounded in justice and human rights. Therefore, the print media's representation of Islam in the context of terrorism is characterised by entrenched patterns of stereotyping, bias, and ideological framing. From Western newsrooms to non-Western media, Islam is disproportionately portrayed as inherently violent and threatening, a narrative that sustains Islamophobia and informs securitization policies globally. This misrepresentation fuels social alienation, exacerbates interfaith tensions, and undermines prospects for peaceful coexistence.

2.4. Print Media Representation of Islam in the Context of Terrorism

Terrorism remains one of the foremost global security challenges of the 21st century, necessitating multifaceted counter-terrorism strategies that engage international organizations, states, and civil society (United Nations [UN], 2023). The United Nations Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy outlines a comprehensive framework aimed at reducing terrorism by integrating prevention, capacity-building, and human rights considerations.

However, beyond state-centric responses, the role of media, especially print media, in framing terrorism, particularly in relation to Islam and Muslim communities, significantly influences public discourse, policymaking, and the efficacy of counter-extremism strategies (Saeed, 2007; Poole, 2002). Islam is the world's second-largest religion, with over two billion adherents accounting for approximately 25 percent of the global population, predominantly residing in Central Asia, the Middle East, North and West Africa, and South Asia (Prayer Times, 2023; Morocco World News, 2023). Pew Research Center (2022) projects Islam as the fastest-growing religion, anticipating that its global population may rival Christianity by 2060, with significant demographic shifts in both Muslim-majority and minority contexts.

Despite this diversity, print media discourses frequently homogenise Muslim populations, overlooking the heterogeneity in ethnic, cultural, political, and theological expressions of Islam (Drennan, n.d.; Miriti, 2008). Central to Islam are the Five Pillars, namely, Shahada (faith declaration), Salat (prayer), Zakat (almsgiving), Sawm (fasting), and Hajj (pilgrimage), which collectively emphasize spiritual devotion, ethical conduct, and social justice (Drennan, n.d.). These pillars reflect core Islamic values of peace, mercy, and community welfare, contrasting sharply with media depictions that conflate Islam with violence and terrorism (Miriti, 2008).

This reductive portrayal contributes to an Islamophobic narrative, which essentialises Islam as inherently violent or extremist. This narrative is not only empirically unfounded but also detrimental to Muslim communities' social integration and identity affirmation (Pew Research Center, 2022; Saeed & Akbarzadeh, 2001). As scholars such as Poole (2002) argued, this monolithic representation erases the complex realities of Muslim lived experiences, thereby perpetuating stereotypes and social exclusion. The portrayal of Muslims as synonymous with terrorism in print media fosters Islamophobia, a phenomenon characterized by prejudice, discrimination, and hostility toward Muslims (Saeed & Akbarzadeh, 2001). Such media narratives not only shape public opinion but also influence the design and implementation of counter-extremism policies (Kundnani, 2014; Poole, 2002).

Empirical studies indicate that media coverage disproportionately attributes terrorist acts to Muslims, while often neglecting other ideological or political motives (Jackson, 2011; Richardson, 2004). This skewed representation legitimises securitised responses, including increased surveillance, racial profiling, and restrictive immigration policies targeting Muslim communities (Kundnani, 2014). For example, in the aftermath of the September 11 attacks, Western media amplified discourses linking Islam to violence, resulting in heightened Islamophobic attitudes and state policies that disproportionately influenced Muslims (Miriti, 2008; Barkun, 2006). The social consequences are profound. For example, Muslim communities often report feelings of marginalisation, alienation, and mistrust toward law enforcement and government institutions (Hafez, 2010; Kundnani, 2014). These dynamics risk exacerbating radicalisation pathways by fostering grievances, thereby undermining community-based counter-extremism initiatives aimed at inclusion and deradicalisation (Kundnani, 2014).

In terrorism reporting, print media often frame Muslims as the 'Other' -irrational, violent, and culturally incompatible, reinforcing Orientalist stereotypes described by Said (1978). This 'Othering' legitimizes exclusionary counter-terrorism policies centered on control, surveillance, and military intervention rather than dialogue and integration (Kabir, Siddique & Alam, 2015). In Kenya, national print media coverage often reflects these global trends, portraying Muslim communities, particularly in coastal and northeastern regions, as sympathetic to or complicit with terrorist groups like Al-Shabaab (Odhiambo et al., 2015, as cited in Kamau, 2023). This framing has influenced Kenyan counter-terrorism strategies that emphasize militarized responses and border security over community development and socio-economic inclusion (Schaeter, 2006). Consequently, this policy orientation risks alienating the very communities whose cooperation is critical for effective counter-extremism.

Research indicates that media-induced fear and stereotyping contribute to public support for restrictive policies, which may undermine civil liberties and human rights (Powell, 2011; Kundnani, 2014). These findings underscore the importance of balanced media portrayals in fostering informed public discourse and enabling policy frameworks that address root causes rather than symptoms of terrorism. Wherefore, the portrayal of Islam and Muslims in print media within the terrorism discourse is a powerful determinant of both public perceptions and the success or failure of counter-extremism strategies. While terrorism remains a multifaceted security challenge, the prevalent media framing that conflates Islam with violence fosters Islamophobia, undermines social cohesion, and complicates inclusive policy responses. Addressing this issue requires coordinated institutional frameworks that regulate media practices, promote ethical journalism, and integrate media literacy into broader counter-terrorism initiatives.

Although Social Identity Theory (SIT) was not developed as a framework to explain terrorism or violent extremism, it offers valuable insights into the dynamics of group behaviour, identity formation, and intergroup relations; critical factors in understanding radicalization processes for this study and therefore answering the second research question. When the media portrays Islam and Muslims through a predominantly negative lens, especially in the context of terrorism, it risks alienating Muslim communities. This perceived stigmatization fosters feelings of marginalization and victimization, prompting some individuals within these communities to regroup in ways that emphasize in-group solidarity, sometimes in opposition to the broader society (Strindberg, 2020). Such media narratives not only affect Muslims.

Non-Muslims who consume content that frequently associates Islam with violence or terrorism may develop fear-based responses, reinforcing in-group/out-group divisions; aligning with the foundational tenet of SIT, arguing

that the individuals' identification with a social group shapes their self-image and perceptions of out-groups, often in ways that exaggerate differences and foster conflict (Strindberg, 2020: 14).

These interactions often lead to the adoption of collective narratives and worldviews, potentially transforming individual grievances into group-based agendas. As Strindberg (2020) notes, "shared experiences may promote cohesive ties, but they can also create or accentuate divisions between 'us' and 'them'" (p. 17). The implications of these dynamics for counter-extremism efforts in Kenya are significant. When certain social groups feel demonized or excluded from national narratives, they may experience an identity crisis.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Since the rise of global terrorism narratives following events such as the September 11 attacks, media representations of Islam have increasingly been intertwined with discourses on extremism and insecurity. This portrayal has promoted distorted ideologies that have stereotyped and marginalised the Muslim community (Picot, 2025). Even though the majority of Muslims have strongly condemned terrorism, public perception in many cases fails to reflect reality. The media still gives prominence to acts of Islamist terrorism compared to other attacks. This has evidently fueled terrorism, radicalisation, and extremism.

Looking at more recent years in 2015, as Picot (2025) further argued, the arrival of refugees from Muslim-minority countries such as Syria, Iraq, Afghanistan, has led to such skewed narratives, hindering the integration and instead fueling isolation, and creating fertile ground for radicalisation. Consequently, such situations have led to increased violent actions and terrorism worldwide. The world has experienced heavy terrorist activities that need to be mitigated. For example, the latest Global Terrorism Index (GTI) Report of 2024 (cited in Otieno, 2024), revealed that in 2023 alone, more than 8,000 terrorism deaths were recorded globally, which was 15% rise from the previous year, 2022. In another report released by GTI (2025), the number of countries experiencing terrorism incidents increased from 58 to 66, with the Islamic State (IS) and its affiliates remaining the deadliest terror organisations globally.

Nevertheless, the report has also established a reduction of terrorism-related deaths to 7,555, which is 13% reduction from 2023. Even though Kenya has improved in tackling terrorism, it remains among the top 20 countries globally most affected by terrorism (GTI, 2025). The GTI Report of 2024 revealed that in 2023 alone, Kenya witnessed some of the worst terror killings in parts of Lamu, Garissa, Wajir, and Mandera; deaths that were meted out by the al-Shabaab terror organisation (Otieno, 2024).

There is growing concern in Kenya that the print media may disproportionately frame Islam within the context of violence, radicalisation, and threat, potentially reinforcing stereotypes and stigmatisation of Muslim communities. Such representations risk oversimplifying complex socio-political dynamics, marginalising over 2 billion Muslim voices globally, and contributing to social exclusion. This framing may also undermine trust between Muslim communities and state security agencies, which is a critical component in effective counter-terrorism efforts, hindering law enforcement and policymakers from building trust and promoting peaceful coexistence between Muslims and non-Muslims.

Despite the central role of media in influencing both public opinion and policy, there is limited empirical research in Kenya that critically examines how Islam is represented in print media, specifically in relation to terrorism, and how such representations impact counter-terrorism strategies. Existing studies often focus broadly on media and terrorism without isolating religious framing or assessing its implications for security policy and community cooperation. This gap in knowledge raises important questions about whether prevailing media narratives contribute to effective counter-terrorism or inadvertently hinder it by fostering alienation, profiling, and resistance among affected communities. Therefore, this study sought to systematically analyse print media representations of Islam in Kenya within the context of terrorism and evaluated their implications on the design, implementation, and effectiveness of counter-terrorism strategies.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design where a mixed research approach was further utilised to collect data. This involved mixing the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches in collecting data; collecting qualitative data first, followed by quantitative data. For Qualitative data, this study analysed the contents of 676 The Nation and Standard newspapers, and further interviewed 24 key informants in who were drawn from media practitioners, security experts, and media scholars. The Standard and Nation were selected for this study since they were the most-read mainstream newspapers in Kenya, according to the Media Council of Kenya (2024) Media Performance report. The study assessed newspapers, both weekend and daily editions, that were published between 2013 and 2020, giving a population of 4,386 copies of the Nation and Standard. However, through Yamane's formula, the study analysed the contents of 676 newspapers as shown below:

Yamane's (1967) formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n=desired sample size; N=the finite size of the population; e=maximum acceptable margin error as determined by researcher (0.05); 1=a theoretical or statistical constant.

Using the formula above, the researcher arrived at a sample size of 676 as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Nation newspaper $n = \frac{2,193}{1 + (2193 \times (0.05)^2)}$

$$n = 338$$

Standard newspaper $n = \frac{2,193}{1 + (2193 \times (0.05)^2)}$

$$n = 338$$

Total of newspaper sample size =676.

The study looked at the newspapers published throughout the whole year of the attack for every strike. The attacks happened in 2013, 2014, 2015, 2019, and 2020. The strikes were the Westgate, Nairobi-Bound bus attack in Mandera, Mpeketoni, Garissa University, Nairobi DusitD2, and Camp Simba. These were the high-profile terror attacks that happened after the 2011 raid on Al Shabaab by the Kenya Defence Forces (KDF) in Somalia (Global Terrorism Index, 2022).

Global Terrorism Index (2022) argued that after the strikes on Al-Shabaab in Somalia, in retaliation, terrorists launched major attacks in Kenya that were widely covered by the media. Therefore, it was important to study the contents of the two mainstream newspapers that reported the attacks. There were two attacks in the year 2020. For Quantitative data, this study used Quantitative Content analysis. Here, the study systematically counted and measured the frequency of specific words and phrases with perceived stereotypes about Islam in relation to terrorism, answering questions such as 'how many', and eventually identifying a meaningful pattern that has helped answer research questions.

5. RESULTS, ANALYSES AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Research results

The findings of this study were guided by the research objectives and questions. The study sampled news stories that were written about terrorist attacks that occurred in Kenya after 2011. The search for both Nation and Standard newspapers in the public libraries and from their online database retrieved a total of 578 newspapers (86%) for the period under study, of a sample size of 676 papers. From the 578 newspapers retrieved, 109 copies (19%) had stories on the terrorist attacks under this study; there were 52 (17%) copies for the Nation and 57 (18%) for the Standard papers.

The 109 papers carried 234 stories about the six attacks. These were both news features and hard news. Hard news had more stories at 133 (57%) while features were 101 (43%). From the analysis, the study found that from the 234 stories analysed, 153 (65%) had content that linked Muslims and Islam to terrorism, while 121 (35%) stories did not. More news feature stories linked Muslims and Islam to terrorism than hard news. From the 153 stories, feature stories had 98 (64%) that linked Islam to terrorism compared to 55 (36%). Through the use of Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing, the study used Interview Schedules to interview all 24 key informants. Out of the 24, 21 (86%) key informants agreed that the newspaper contents under this study portrayed Muslims and Islam as terrorism sympathisers, while 3 (14%) disagreed.

5.2. Analysis and Discussions

5.2.1. Print Media Representation of Islam in the context of terrorism

In the content analysis of the two papers, in the spirit of gatekeeping theory, reporters and editors allowed words and phrases, such as 'jihadist, Islamic prayers, Islamic terrorists, and recitation of Islamic prayers' to pass to the audience. These are the contents that attract the attention of the public into believing that Islam is either a terrorist or a sympathiser of terrorism. For example, a story in Nation (2019, January 16; p.3) about the DusitD2 attack in Nairobi associates the al-Shabaab activities with Sharia law. Sharia law is an Islamic legal system developed from the Quran and the Sunna, which are the Prophet Mohammed's teachings.

The story partly read, 'if al-Shabaab, which controls rural areas especially in Southern Somalia under strict intervention of Sharia law, is responsible for yesterday's attack, it only proves that the war on terror is far from over.' This piece links al-Shabaab to Islam after bringing in the aspect of Sharia law. Since Sharia law is Islamic, mentioning it in relations al-Shabaab terrorism attack in this way associates Islam with the acts of terrorism. Covering the same attack, the Standard newspaper (January 20, 2019: 4) partly wrote, 'blown up into smithereens, the 25-year-old Mahir Khalid Riziki was born and brought up in the Majengo area of Mombasa town. Police say it is while attending prayers at Musa Mosque that Mahir met recruiter, Ramadhan Hamisi Kufungwa, now in Somalia fighting alongside al-Shabaab and inviting more Kenyan recruits.' In this piece, a Mosque is associated with the recruitment of terrorists. Mosques are the worship places for Muslims. Therefore, in a story where a terrorist is argued to have met his recruiter in a Mosque, it is associating Islam with acts of terrorism, such as recruitment. This is similar to what this study found during the interviews with the key informants. For example, a Christian pastor, Participant A, argued that Standard and the Nation have portrayed Islam negatively in the context of terrorism.

He observed that since newspapers started covering terrorist attacks heavily in Kenya, he has a perception that Muslims are the perpetrators of terrorism, 'we read stories that indicate that suspects are Muslims or those who have first converted to Islam. In fact, I still believe that for me to operate effectively as a terrorist, I must join Islam. Look at the terms used in the stories-words and phrases such as jihadist, Islamic group, training and recruitment; we read that they are conducted in the Mosques. These are all linking Muslims and Islam to terrorism.'

This description was also evident in a story carried in the Nation newspaper (September 22, 2013) when covering the Westgate Mall attack. The reporter quoted a witness who described the physique of the attackers and went ahead to quote what the attacker said, a sentiment that associates Islam with terrorism. The piece read, 'they looked like Somalis. They were young and slender. They chanted Allahu Akbar (God is great) as they entered the building' (p.3). Allahu Akbar is an Islamic prayer (God is great). This piece indicates that the attackers were not just terrorists, but Muslims who were strong believers in Islam as a religion; those are most likely seeking God's intervention as they execute terrorism activities.

In another Westgate attack story by the Standard newspaper (September 27, 2013; p.4), the Islamic religion is associated with terrorism activities. It reads, 'security report named Sheikh Abidewil Mohammed, Sheikh Hassan as the masterminds of the plot....they are being assisted by Sheikh Hassan alias Blackie of Majengo and Omar Ahmed Ali alias Jerry who are currently staying near Mamba Petrol Station and Huruma Mosque along Juja road.' This story has used the words Sheikh, and Mosque. These are critical words in Islam as a religion. A Sheikh is an Islamic

religious leader. This story quotes security reports validating the involvement of the Islamic religious leaders in planning a terrorist attack. The Sheikhs are further said to be living in a Mosque along Juja road. The story is not only trying to identify the suspects but also associating the same suspects with the Islamic religion. Apart from informing readers that Muslims are the perpetrators of terrorism, this kind of story goes deeper to tell how the senior-most Islamic religious leaders are assisting in terror masterminds.

This study then sought the opinion of a Sheikh based in Migori town, Migori County, Kenya, Participant B. The Sheikh admitted that the Kenyan media has put Islam and Muslims on the radar of terrorism. He added that Islam is a religion under siege. "Nation and Standard, during the coverage of the terror attacks, have portrayed Islam as a religion of violence that supports terrorism. Who does not know that Muslims are the perpetrators of terrorism in Kenya? And who spreads this message if not our newspapers?" He, however, absolved Islam from organising terrorism attacks, 'Our religion is falsely under siege. As a Sheikh, I am not happy because journalists have refused to dig deeper in order to understand Islam and its teachings against acts of violence such as terrorism. A genuine Sheikh cannot support terrorism. Those using the title 'Sheikhs' and supporting terrorism are fake Sheikhs, and journalists should not rely on them.'

He observed that there is a need for more training for journalists on matters of religion to avoid associating religious doctrines with violence, "media stakeholders need to organise religion-based workshops and invite relevant scholars like us to train journalists on matters of religion and terrorism so that they know what jihadist is, among other religious issues."

This kind of reporting has forced the Kenyan government to come up with policies, ethical issues, and laws that are expected to shape the way journalists report terrorist attacks. These include the Code of Ethics for the Practice of Journalism in Kenya under the Media Council of Kenya Act (23), the Constitution of Kenya Act 34 (1) and 33 (2), which generally argue that freedom of expression and speech does not extend to propaganda, incitement to violence, hate speech, or advocacy of hatred.

There is also the Prevention of Terrorism Act (2012), Security Law (Amendment) Bill, 2014, among others, which are aimed at avoiding the portrayal of Muslims and Islam as terror sympathisers. For example, in the Prevention of Terrorism Act (2012; 30(a)), a person who publishes or utters a statement that is likely to be understood as directly or indirectly encouraging or inducing another person to commit or prepare to commit an act of terrorism commits an offence and is liable on conviction to imprisonment for a term not exceeding 14 years. Similar sentiments have also been echoed in the Media Council of Kenya Act 23 (Acts of Violence) that the media shall avoid presenting acts of violence, armed robberies, banditry and terrorist activities in a manner that glorifies such anti-social conduct.

President Uhuru Kenyatta further intervened by signing into law the Security Bill, an anti-terrorism legislation which required journalists to first obtain police permission before publishing stories on domestic terrorism, as was reported by the BBC (2014, January 19).

The existence of such a law was confirmed further during the data collection from the key informants. Out of 24 key informants, 22 (92%) agreed that there were laws in place to guide journalists on terror reporting. Only 2 (8%) did not know. Participant T, a senior journalist with one of the papers under study, argued that, 'even though journalists have a grasp of all these laws and ethics, some still lack detailed knowledge, especially on matters of terrorism. For example, some journalists still do not know much about Anti-Terrorism acts; there should be proper civic education.'

Another key informant, Participant L, a reporter, observed that, 'journalists ignore these crucial laws and infuse their personal feelings.' This argument is similar to what the study found from a media scholar, Participant Q, who works with the Kenya Correspondents Association (KCA). He averred that even though journalists are aware of these laws, and some have even been officially sensitised, they still ignore them. He argued that even journalists who have been sensitised about these laws still ignore them when reporting, "media ethics training has all these frameworks. These are things journalists are introduced to in colleges and universities, but still ignore. Many

journalists are careless and have a false sense of entitlement, and there is need for serious action to be taken against those who go against these laws.'

When interviewed about the laws and polices available vis-a-viz journalists' reporting on terror attacks in Kenya, Participant Q, who works with the National Counter-Terrorism Unit (NCTU) argued that it has been carelessness of journalists because laws are there, but no one is adhering to them, 'there have been major howlers by journalists while reporting on terrorism related news out of combination of zeal and ignorance in the past. As a Unit, we are now forced to go directly to the people, using vernacular radios to talk to the people about terrorism and religion. This is what should be highly encouraged, and we have been receiving positive responses. But other local vernacular media outlets can also be engaged, such as newspapers, televisions, books, film, and drama.'

Participant Q further advised journalists to read the available rules regarding terrorism reporting so that they do not mess up their coverage. For example, according to the Media Council of Kenya Act 2013, Article 21 (Use of pictures and names), 'as a general rule, the media shall apply caution in the use of pictures and names, and shall avoid publication when there is a possibility of harming the persons concerned.' The Media Council of Kenya has gone further to identify some of the words that should not be used in news stories, namely, 'jihadist', 'Islamist', and 'kaffir', among others.

However, looking at some of the stories about the terror attacks under this study, these rules by the MCK have been ignored by the reporters and their editors. Kenyan newspapers, therefore, have promoted the ideology and hegemony that have represented Islam as a terrorism sympathiser; a situation that has led to negative perception against Islam and has eventually fueled enmity, terrorism, inter-faith tension, and violent extremism. The findings from this study, through the theory of Gatekeeping, have answered the first objective and first research question of the study. It is therefore invaluable to indicate that Gatekeeping theory has provided an effective understanding of how reporters went out to the field to cover the terrorist attacks, chose what they felt was more newsworthy, and, during writing and editing, let the contents reach the audience. This editorial gatekeeping stage has critical implications, as it may contribute to negative portrayals that influence public attitudes, as has been evident in the representation of Islam regarding terrorism in Kenya.

5.2.2. Print Media Representation of Islam in the context of terrorism

Out of the 24 key informants interviewed, 23 (96%) agreed that indeed the news stories could create fear among Muslims and non-Muslims, while 1 (4%) disagreed. Again, from the 24 key informants, 18 (75%) agreed that the news stories published in the newspapers have the potential to fuel acts of terrorism, while 6 (25%) said they cannot.

The way terror attack stories have been framed in the newspapers under this study was highly likely to create fear, as has been found out from respondents. The Muslims were portrayed as killers, those who threaten and are ready to eliminate whoever they feel is not supporting Islam as a religion. A story about the Mpeketoni raid, published by the Nation on September 7, 2014, and September 17, indicated that terrorism group, al-Shabaab, was fighting those suspected of oppressing Muslims. In the story, the al-Shabaab terrorists claimed responsibility and warned 'the attack was in revenge for the oppression of Muslims.' This kind of story is double-barreled. As non-Muslims feel scared and fearful of Muslims who are portrayed as roaming around to kill the 'oppressors', Muslims, on the other hand, are incited that they are being oppressed and they should wake up to fight the 'oppressors' who are out to finish them.

This story can lead to fear and would most likely promote more acts of terrorism and other acts of violent extremism, where those who feel offended would gang against the perceived enemies. In an interview with one of the sheikhs, it was revealed that newspaper stories that have portrayed Muslims as terrorists have led to more interfaith tension and enmity between Muslims and non-Muslims. The Sheikh based in Nairobi, a Participant L, averred that non-Muslims fear Muslims too much to the extent that Muslims are sidelined in jobs, and even in business deals, 'these are the kind of things that can also annoy some Muslim youth to now engage in the unlawful acts of violence since they believe there is nothing they can get while they are not terrorists. We cannot get jobs easily,

and we are chased away from business deals because we are seen as terrorists. This Islamophobic attitude can make people fight against those they feel are more pampered.'

In a candid interview with an Islamic Law and Jurisprudence scholar in Saudi Arabia, Participant H, the perception that Muslims are bad and aiding terrorism is untrue and can interfere with inter-faith dialogue efforts that are going on across the globe. He argued that the perception is based on lies spread by the media, 'we as Muslims do not know about terrorism because it is not Islamic. What these terrorists do is totally opposite to what Islam teaches. They even go against Islam and Jihadism; they conduct suicide bombing, kill children, murder women and the elderly, all against Islamic warfare etiquette. When the media accuses Islam of this, it creates mistrust and some may decide to fight back in revenge. This hugely affects inter-faith dialogues and instead promotes violent extremism.'

This argument was echoed by another participant, L, another Muslim. He said he would obviously fight back because Muslims are belittled and looked down upon; always seen as very violent and terrorists, 'yes, I will do it (terrorism). What do I do if they feel I am a terrorist? Out of bitterness, I will attack now, and will attack the accusers violently.'

A security expert, Participant O, based at the Kenya National Counter-Terrorism Centre, argued that, indeed, the news stories portraying Muslims as terrorists have made it difficult to combat terrorism. He remarked that currently, there are programmes being rolled out to make people understand who the terrorists are; to make it clear that terrorism is not faith-based, 'we are trying to engage the community and vernacular media, especially radios, to make people understand more about terrorism. It is not faith-based, and people should know that. The media content is making things worse. It is not easy to convince people that Muslims are good people in relation to terrorism.'

The observation by media and security scholar, Participant N, about how Kenyan newspapers covered Muslims in regards to terrorism was that the stories were poorly framed and were 'chaotic' meant to 'promote violence in Kenya', 'how do you always portray Muslims as terrorists, the killers; and at the same time tell non-Muslims that Muslims are looking for you, to murder you because you are not in Islam? If you keep accusing someone of something they do not do, then they may end up doing it out of anger or to prove a point that they can do it, just to make you annoyed.'

The perception that Muslims are the terrorists has led to fear, more so Islamophobia, which is argued to have resulted in a number of terrorism cases in the world. Hate crimes against Muslims across the globe have been on the rise, affecting Islam, which is the world's second-largest religion after Christianity (Samari, 2016). Muslims have been harassed in learning institutions, mosques have been destroyed, and Muslim charities have had their assets frozen (Samari, 2016). These findings, through the theory of Social Identity, answer the second objective and second research question of the study. Social Identity Theory helps explain how people would form a group against an opposing one when they feel not valued and disregarded. When Muslims in Kenya feel demonised and devalued in the media, they may react defensively, sometimes through radicalisation or acts of terrorism as a form of retaliation, as evident in this study. On the other hand, non-Muslims may also feel that Muslims are a threat to their lives and stand to fight back. This dynamic significantly undermines counter-terrorism efforts and complicates peacebuilding initiatives in the region.

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

This study has revealed that Standard and Nation newspapers' representations have associated Islam with terrorism. Theoretically, these findings utilise Gatekeeping and Social Identity theories, illustrating how continuous exposure to such Islamic portrayals is likely to shape the audience's perceptions of Islam as a religion of violence. Practically, these findings have suggested that unbalanced media narratives are likely to contribute to scenarios where extremist groups such as the al-Shabaab can terrorise, therefore, prompting the need for terrorism-conflict journalism aimed at improving counter-extremism strategies.

7. CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study contributes to policy and advocacy development by providing actionable recommendations for journalists, government agencies, and key media stakeholders, which include the Media Council of Kenya (MCK), Kenya Union of Journalists (KUJ), and Kenya Correspondents Association (KCA), to formulate evidence-based policies that enhance terrorism reporting in Kenya. Since it has addressed ethical and representational challenges in news coverage, the findings aim to foster more responsible and conflict-sensitive journalism. For media and communication scholars, this research bridges a critical knowledge gap by examining the intersection of terrorism reporting, religious bias, and media framing, an under-explored area in existing literature.

Additionally, the study has advocated for curriculum reforms in tertiary institutions, proposing the integration of religion-sensitive journalism and terrorism-sensitive reporting into journalism and media programmes in the learning institutions. Such academic advancements will equip future journalists with the necessary skills to report on terrorism and religion with nuance, thereby contributing to national cohesion, security, and Kenya's Big Four Agenda (Government of Kenya, 2020) in food security, affordable healthcare, housing, and manufacturing. Beyond academia, this research challenges harmful narratives that wrongly associate Islam with terrorism in Kenya. In advocating for interfaith dialogue initiatives through media engagement, the study aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 16, promoting peace, justice, and strong institutions (UNDP, 2023). It also supports the African Union's Agenda 2063 (Aspiration 7), which envisions a peaceful, democratic, and innovative Africa (African Union, 2021). Therefore, this work underscores the media's role in fostering social harmony, countering extremism, and strengthening national and global security frameworks.

8. RECOMMENDATION

Firstly, the study recommends the establishment of terrorism-sensitive Journalism. Even though there is conflict-sensitive journalism theory, but it is wider and covers other conflicts, including domestic and political acts of violence. It could be the main reason why journalists may not feel attached to matters of terrorism. The development of terrorism-sensitive journalism would involve deeper religious doctrines that should be looked into when covering terrorism.

Secondly, there is a need to have Religion Journalism in all colleges and universities offering journalism. Religion Journalism is a kind of journalism that enables journalists to have knowledge on news coverage of different religious issues, doctrines, and practices in order to promote inter-faith tolerance and to minimise cases of violent extremism, terrorism, and radicalisation that might arise because of insensitive news reporting and ignorance on matters of religion.

Thirdly, it is important for the relevant stakeholders, such as the law enforcers and the Media Council of Kenya, to ensure these laws are followed strictly when reporting on terrorist attacks. Journalists, like in Medicine, Law, and Education, should be given practising licences so that whoever breaches the laws will have their licenses revoked and not allowed to practise anymore. Moreover, media houses should develop and or strengthen their own terrorism-reporting policies for the reporters so that they can counter-check with the news narratives before going to the press to ensure the content given to the audience is rich and does not fuel conflict and tension.

Finally, civic education and more training on the existing laws, ethics, and policies related to interfaith dialogue should be enhanced. The government and other stakeholders should ensure local communities in both urban and rural areas are educated on matters of religion and inter-religious tolerance as a way of reducing faith-based conflicts such as terrorism. This can be achieved by the use of vernacular media outlets such as radios, newspapers, film, drama, among others.

9. CONCLUSION

The study found that the stories were framed in a way that Islam was viewed as a perpetrator. This finding revealed the gap in gatekeeping and framing when covering acts of terrorism in Kenya. It further revealed that newspapers

under study used terms such as 'jihadis,' 'Islamists,' and informed the readers that terrorists were being recruited in the mosques by Muslims. Consequently, this portrayal of Muslims as terrorists has had a negative impact in Kenya. The newspaper audience has a perception that Muslims are bad people, creating too much fear and fueling islamophobia in Kenya. This can easily trigger tensions and violence between Muslims and non-Muslims. Therefore, as the study has found, this scenario has hindered the efforts of the Kenyan government in combating terrorism and extremism.

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